

A new spot test for the semi-quantification of dithiocarbamates residues in traces in soil samples of potato growing field

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A selective, sensitive, simple and inexpensive spot test is described for the detection of mancozeb at trace levels in soil, vegetation and water. It is based upon the intensive catalytic action of dithiocarbamates on the production of nitrogen from sodium azide reaction with iodine.

Spectrophotometry¹, gas chromatography² and electro-chemical method³ have been used for the quantification of dithiocarbamates. However, spot test analysis has been found to be extremely useful for the preliminary characterization of the text material. We report herein a simple and inexpensive spot test for the detection and semi-quantitative determination of dithiocarbamate fungicides.

Results and Discussion

It is known⁴ that the following reaction is catalyzed by inorganic sulfides, thiosulfates and thiocyanates (C=S or C-SH group), while thioethers (R-S-R), thiosulfides (R-S-S-R), sulfones (R-SO₂-R), sulfinic acids (R-SO₂H) and sulfonic acids (R-SO₃H) are found to be ineffective.

Thus the vigorous evolution of bubbles of nitrogen in the reaction permits the detection of compounds containing C=S or C-SH group. Now this reaction has been reinvestigated and utilized in the analysis of pesticide residues.

The results show that mancozeb (0.05 g) can be detected in presence of (a) acids (barbituric, gallic, hippuric, isocitric, malic, phthalic, succinic, sulfanilic and tartaric acid), (b) alcohols (1-butanol, 1-propanol, 1-ethanol and methanol), (c) aldehydes (benzaldehyde, 4-dimethyl-aminobenzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and vanillin), (d) amides (dimethylformamide, salicylamide, thiourea and urea), (e) amines (aniline, diethylaniline, indole, nicotine and trimethylamine), (f) diethylether, (g) pyridine, (h) hydrocarbons (benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chlorobenzene, *o*-toluidine and paraffin), (i) ketones (acetone and acetophenone), (j) mineral acids (hydrochloric and sulfuric acids), (k) oils and fats (mustard oil and ghee), (l) pesticides (bavistin, carbaryl, phenoxyacetic acid, trichloroacetic acid,

endosulfan, phamidon and chlorpyrifos), (m) phenols (catechol, 1-naphthol, 2-naphthol, phenol, *p*-nitrophenol and resorcinol), (n) inorganic compounds (aluminium ammonium sulfate, ammonium sulfate, barium sulfate, cupric sulfate, ferrous sulfate, hydrazine sulfate, manganese sulfate, magnesium sulfate, nickel sulfate, potassium hydrogen sulfate, sodium bicarbonate, sodium sulfate, sodium thiosulfate and zinc sulfate), (o) leaves (bakayan, babbool, neem and tulsi) and (p) soils.

Besides mancozeb, (i) gallic acid, (ii) hippuric acid, (iii) thiourea, (iv) ferrous sulfate, (v) hydrazine sulfate, (vi) sodium thiosulfate and (vii) neem leave extract give positive response by thin layer chromatographic detection (TLC) and compounds (iii)-(vii) give positive response by watch-glass and capillary methods. Thus the latter methods are more selective than test tube detection (TTAU), TLC and paper chromatographic (PC) detection.

The sensitivity sequence for detection of mancozeb ($\mu\text{g}/0.1 \text{ ml}$) was found to be : watch glass (0.38) > capillary (0.45) > TLC (0.75) and PC (0.75) > TTAU (67.5). The TTAU provides two signals (bubble and decolorization), TLC provides two signals (bubble and its pit), PC (decolourization), watch glass (bubble) and capillary (bubble) provide only one signal.

The results of detection on TLC of varying thickness (0.25-0.5 mm) show that the better results are obtained on thick layers. The lower limit of detection of mancozeb was found to be 7.5, 0.38-7.5, 0.38-7.5, 0.38-0.75, 0.38-75, 0.38. 0.38-75, 0.38. 0.75-75, 0.38 and 0.38 $\mu\text{g}/0.1 \text{ ml}$ on the layer of aluminium oxide basic, barium sulfate, barium oxide, calcium carbonate, calcium citrate, calcium sulfate, cellulose, ferric oxide, silica gel G, soil and titanium oxide, respectively, by TLC detection. Hence it is clear that mancozeb in traces can be detected by soil TLC. The lower

limit of detection of zinc dimethyl dithiocarbamate, copper dimethyl dithiocarbamate, ferric dimethyl dithiocarbamate, manganese dimethyldithiocarbamate, zinc morpholine dithiocarbamate, copper morpholine dithiocarbamate, ferric morpholine dithiocarbamate, manganese morpholine dithiocarbamate and zinc diphenyl dithiocarbamate was found to be 10 : 0.8 : 0.8, 10 : 8.0 : 8.0, 1.0 : 0.1 : 0.1, 1.0 : 0.1 : 0.1, 0.1 : 0.3 : 0.3, 1.0 : 0.5 : 0.5, 1.0 : 0.5 : 0.5, 0.1 : 0.1 : 0.1 and 0.6 : 0.4 : 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/0.1$ ml on TLC : watch glass : capillary.

Several soil and vegetation samples were collected from the potato growing fields where mancozeb and its admixtures were used as fungicides. The leaves of the freshly spread potato plants showed the positive test for mancozeb. The test also showed the presence of mancozeb residues in soil where potato crops were grown for the last three years continuously.

Conclusion : Amongst the techniques under study, the watch glass detection is simpler, faster and more inexpensive for the detection of mancozeb residues in soil, vegetation and water. The detection can be directly performed on field, i.e. on the surface of leaves, fruits etc. and at least 100 samples can be detected within one hour. The present concentration of mancozeb has been found to be $\cong 10 \mu\text{g}/5$ g in soil and vegetation by using this test.

Experimental

Sodium azide (5%) was dissolved in ethanol : water (3 : 7) containing iodine (1.27%) and potassium iodide (2 g). Aqueous suspension (1%) of mancozeb was used. All the chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. grade. TLC plates were prepared and samples were collected as usual⁵. TTAU test was performed in a test tube (9.8 m \times 1.2 cm i.d.) armed with a side U-tube (16.9 cm \times 0.3 cm i.d.) by the following procedure. A portion of the test material (0.05 ml or 0.05 g) was taken in the test tube, moisture was removed

by mild heating. Then 10 M H_2SO_4 (0.05 ml) was added to it and the reagent (0.1 ml) was filled in the side-tube. The main tube was stoppered, then heated and the change in colour of the reagent as well as the bubble formation was noted. TLC and PC detections were made by placing a drop of the reagent over the drop of the test material. In the capillary detection, firstly solution or slurry of the test material and then the reagent were filled by capillarity force. The nature of the bubble and air gap produced at the junction of test material and the reagent was recorded. Mancozeb in traces was detected on the surface of leaves and fruits by placing a drop of the reagent directly on the leave.

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